

Fermat's Principle and Loss of Information Part 2

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In this note, we try to show that the maximization of entropy in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case subject to $\sum_i p(i)=1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ is really mathematically identical to Fermat's law applied to 2-dimensional refraction (i.e. Snell's law). In particular, we argue that both approaches are based on two constraints. In the MB case, the variable in question is $p(i)$, the probability, and in the Fermat case x_1, x_2 . In both cases, one considers $p(i)$ and $p(i)+dp(i)$ or x_1, x_2 and x_1+dx_1, x_2+dx_2 as solutions up to first order in dp or dx_1, dx_2 . It is thus the Taylor series expansion which brings in the d/dp or d/dx derivatives.

In the MB case, one might argue that one has an entropy function which is maximized subject to two constraints, but we argue that one may consider $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$ with $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$ which is $-1/T$ multiplied by the energy constraint. Thus, one is really using the energy constraint, but writing it in terms of $p(i)$ so that one may consider the two solutions $p(i)$ and $p(i)+dp(i)$ as both satisfying the two constraints.

Consider now the Fermat case. Imagine that one is given a starting point $(x=0, y_1)$ and an end point $(x=L, y_2)$ with an n_1-n_2 interface along the x -axis at $y=0$. $x=0, y_1$ and y_2 may be chosen arbitrarily, but L should follow from the correct solution (or experimental result), but is introduced as a parameter. Pictorially one expects the result to be in terms of angles and so exact values of y_1, y_2 and L should ultimately give way to an incident and refracted angle. Similarly, the correct solution takes an overall time and this also should follow from an experimental result (although one would usually not know this number given the high speed of light.)

In the Fermat case, one considers writing $t_1+t_2 = n_1/c \sqrt{y_1^2 + x_1^2} + n_2/c \sqrt{y_2^2 + x_2^2}$ with x_1 and x_2 able to change subject to the constraint $x_1+x_2=L$. In other words, one considers an experimental t_1+t_2 corresponding to experimental x_1, x_2 values and considers x_1+dx_1, x_2+dx_2 such that t_1+t_2 does not change. The maximization condition $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx=0$ is really a Taylor expansion of $t_1(x)$ and $t_2(x)$ such that x_1+dx and x_2+dx do not change the value of t_1+t_2 . This then leads to a special condition for x_1, x_2 with $x_1+x_2=L$.

In other words, the mathematics of the maximization of entropy subject to constraints, where the entropy is really an expression of one of the constraints ($\sum_i e_i p(i)$) with $-e_i/T$ replaced by $h(p(i))$ so $p(i)$ can be changed is the same mathematics which is used in the Fermat principle for 2-dimensional refraction, we argue.

Analysis of the MB Case

The MB (Maxwell-Boltzmann) distribution is often said to follow from maximizing entropy subject to constraints:

$$\sum_i p(i)=1 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave} \quad ((1b))$$

The entropy is given by: $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$. ((2)) The point we make is that for an unnormalized $p(i)$, the entropy is really the same as the second constraint ((1b)) multiplied by $-1/T$, but now written as $h(p(i)) p(i)$ with $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$. The point seems to be that one may

consider $p(i)$ and $p(i)+dp(i)$ which yield the same Eave and satisfy $\text{Sum over } i \ p(i) = 1$. If one considers:

$$\text{Sum over } i \ \{p(i)+dp(i)\} h(p(i)+dp(i)) \quad ((3))$$

then this may be expanded as a Taylor series up to first order in the function $p(i)$. This yields:

$$\text{Eave} + \text{Sum over } i \ h(p(i)) dp(i) + \text{Sum over } i \ dh/dp(i) p(i) dp(i) \quad ((4))$$

If one insists that ((3)) should also equal Eave, i.e. there is a second solution $p(i)+dp(i)$ which yields the same constraint values as $p(i)$, then the second term of ((4)) is automatically 0 from $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i dp(i) = 0$ and one must insist that:

$$p(i) dh/dp(i) = 1 \rightarrow h(p) = \ln(p) \text{ or } p(i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ the MB result } ((5))$$

Thus, the maximization subject to constraints seems to be really the case of insisting on two solutions $p(i)$ and $p(i)+dp(i)$ satisfying the same initial two constraints (with the second satisfying them only up to a first order expansion in $dp(i)$). This then yields conditions on $p(i)$ which allow for its unique solution. We argue that the identical math appears in Fermat's least time approach applied to 2-dimensional refraction.

Fermat's Principle and 2-Dimensional Refraction

Consider 2-dimensional refraction with light starting at x_1, y_1 , reaching an n_1-n_2 (index of refraction) interface along the x-axis at $y=0$ and then moving to y_2, L . In such a case, L is presumably a value supplied from experiment, but we consider it as a number here. The Fermat approach is to consider that one does not know x at $y=0$ and to minimize time. Again one formally sees a minimization appear, but we try to consider the problem in terms of two solutions x and $x+dx$.

Consider the constraints in the problem:

$$x_1+x_2=L \text{ where } x_2=L-x_1 \text{ and } x_1 \text{ is really } x \quad ((6a))$$

$$\text{Secondly, } t_1+t_2=\text{experimental time} = n_1/c \sqrt{y_1^2+x_1^2} + n_2/c \sqrt{y_2^2+x_2^2} \quad ((6b))$$

Like with the MB case, the idea seems to be that if there is an x_1, x_2 solution to two constraints ((6a)) and ((6b)), then there is also an x_1+dx_1, x_2+dx_2 solution and this then imposes a unique value for x . The math is identical to the MB case. One has two constraints in the MB case and considers $p(i)+dp(i)$. Here one again has two constraints and considers $x_i + dx_i$ while insisting that t_1+t_2 does not change its value. Then ((6b)) with

$x_1 \rightarrow x_1+dx_1$ and $x_2 \rightarrow x_2+dx_2$ is:

$$(t_1+t_2) + n_1/c \ 2 \ x_1 \ dx_1 / \sqrt{y_1^2+x_1^2} + n_2/c \ 2 \ x_2 \ dx_2 / \sqrt{y_2^2+x_2^2} \quad ((7))$$

For ((7)) to yield (t_1+t_2) with $dx_1+dx_2=0$, one requires:

$$n_1 \frac{x_1}{\sqrt{y_1^2+x_1^2}} = n_2 \frac{x_2}{\sqrt{y_2^2+x_2^2}} \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is Snell's law obtained directly from the two constraints in the same manner as the MB case which also uses two constraints. In other words, the entropy used in MB case is really $-1/T$ multiplied by the Sum over i $e^{-e_i/T} p(i)$ = eave constraint with $-e_i/T$ replaced with $h(p(i))$ so that $p(i)$ and $p(i)+dp(i)$ may be considered as solutions. The math, based on two constraints, is identical.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Fermat's principle applied to 2-dimensional refraction (Snell's law) and the MB maximization of entropy are really the identical math process. Both introduce two constraints. In the MB case, which at first appears as the maximization of entropy - Sum over i $p(i) \ln(p(i))$ subject to Sum over i $p(i)=1$ and Sum over i $e_i p(i)$, one really has $\ln(p(i)) = h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$. In other words, the entropy is a really $-1/T$ multiplied by the Sum over i $e_i p(i)$ constraint from unnormalized $p(i)$. Thus, one really has a two constraint problem.

This allows one to consider $p(i)$ and $p(i) + dp(i)$ as solutions to this constraint leading to a unique solution for $p(i)$, i.e $C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

In the Fermat case, we suggest that one again has two constraints: t_1+t_2 =experimental number = $n_1/c \sqrt{y_1^2+x_1^2} + n_2/c \sqrt{y_2^2+x_2^2}$ and $x_1+x_2=L$. One may consider an x_1, x_2 solution and an x_1+dx_1, x_2+dx_2 solution as both satisfying the constraints to first order in dx_1, dx_2 and this then leads to a unique solution for x_1, x_2 .

In other words, both approaches, the MB MaxEnt case and Fermat's principle applied to 2-dimensional refraction are really both cases of two constraints with solutions for a variable v and $v+dv$, hence leading to a unique solution for v .